

SMARTER GOALS FOR BETTER FUTURE

35th EACD
Annual Meeting
European Academy of
Childhood Disability
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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 **University
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CONTENTS

Welcome Address	iv
Committees	v
Sponsors	vii
Abstracts	viii
Table of Contents	1
Keynote Lectures	21
Oral Communication	27
Poster Presentations	172
Author index	506

WELCOME ADDRESS

Dear Colleagues and Friends!

On behalf of the Scientific and Organizing committee of the 35th European Academy of Childhood Disability (EACD) Annual Meeting, it is a privilege and great pleasure to welcome you to Ljubljana, from May 24th to 27th 2023.

I would like to thank you for giving us the opportunity to host this event. Following the outstanding line of previous EACD annual meetings, we will do our best in offering an excellent opportunity to share experiences, exchange scientific ideas, and foster interactions between all professionals, children and their families.

The motto of this EACD annual meeting is "Smarter Goals for Better Future", with the intent to emphasize the importance of goal setting in all processes of care in the rehabilitation of children and youth.

Further, it is a great pleasure to announce a number of excellent keynotes with prestigious professionals in the field of childhood-onset disability.

Slovenia, your host country, tells its green story. Everything is green no matter which direction you turn – towards the Alpine peaks and extensive forests, the Adriatic Sea, the mysterious Karst and nearby vineyards, and the Pannonian Plain. Ljubljana

Ljubljana, the capital city, is a vibrant city with thousands of years of history. The European Green Capital 2016 has in a short time become a model of livability and eco-sustainability for all medium-sized cities in Europe. Our conference venue is in the city center, which is closed to traffic.

On behalf of the European Academy of Childhood Disability – EACD and University Rehabilitation Institute Republic of Slovenia, we look forward to welcoming you to the 35th EACD Conference!

Yours faithfully,

Asist. prof. Katja Groleger Sršen, MD, PhD

President of the Local Scientific and Organizing Committee

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BAUSCH HEALTH

Art therapy in child (re)habilitation

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Introduction: The application of art therapy in the multidisciplinary process of (re)habilitation has proven to be successful in patients with diseases of the central and peripheral nervous system, but it is still insufficiently used in daily clinical work. The aim of the work was to show the application of art therapy in the (re)habilitation of children and youth.

Patients and Methods: The research was conducted at the Children's Habilitation and Rehabilitation Clinic of the Institute for Health Care of Children and Youth of Vojvodina Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, during the period of the current covid-19 pandemic, March-September 2020. The respondents independently chose the drawing technique, the number of drawings, as well as the topic.

Results: 33 respondents participated in the research: 27 children (14 boys and 13 girls) and 6 caregivers. Of these, 14 children (51.85%) were treated in outpatient settings, and 13 (48.15%) in inpatient settings. In the total sample, 8 respondents (24.24%) were aged 3-6 years, 8 (24.24%) aged 7-10 years, 6 (18.18%) aged 11-14 years, and 11 (33.34%) older than 15 years. A total of 45 drawings were obtained during the (re)habilitation process. The most common was drawing with wooden crayons, 18 drawings (40%) and ballpoint pen, 10 drawings (22.22%).

Conclusion: Involving hands in bimanual drawing activities, improving attention and motivation when working in a small group can be an additional tool in the treatment and (re)habilitation process.

Relevance for users and families:

Involving hands in bimanual drawing activities, improving attention and motivation when working in a small group can be an additional tool in the treatment and (re)habilitation process.